

Causes and treatment of pylorstenosis

Ergasheva Nigorxon

Jo'rayeva Lobar

Teachers of the Technical College of Public Health

named after Abu Ali ibn Sino

Annotation: Pyloric stenosis is an uncommon condition in infants that blocks food from entering the small intestine. Typically, a muscular valve between the stomach and small intestine holds food in the stomach until it is ready for the next stage in the digestive process. This valve is called the pylorus valve. In pyloric stenosis, the pylorus muscles thicken and become abnormally large, blocking food from reaching the small intestine.

Key words: pyloric, food, disease, baby, stenosis, muscles, stomach.

Pylorostenosis is a disease characterized by narrowing of the opening from the stomach to the beginning of the small intestine (pylorus). The first symptoms of the disease are "fountain-like" vomiting without bile. This symptom mainly occurs after feeding the baby. Symptoms clearly appear in the period from two weeks to twelve weeks of the baby. The cause of pyloric stenosis is not clear. Risk factors include babies being born by Caesarean section, being born prematurely, and being artificially fed. As a result of the thickening of the walls of the pyloric canal of the stomach, it is possible to identify a formation with an olive-shaped dense thick consistency. This finding is often confirmed by ultrasound.

<http://innoconferences.iblogger.org/>

Treatment initially begins with correcting dehydration and electrolyte problems. Then, depending on the course of the disease, conservative treatment measures are performed with surgery or atropine. 1-2 out of every 1,000 babies are affected, and boys are four times more likely than girls. This condition is rarely observed in adults. . Pyloric stenosis was first described in 1888, and surgical treatment was first performed in 1912 by Conrad Ramstedt. Many babies died before surgical treatment was discovered. The symptoms of pylorostenosis are mainly manifested by the vomiting symptom that is getting worse in the period from the first week to 6 months of life of babies with the disease. This disease is observed in boys 4 times more often than in girls. Vomiting is often non-bilious and is described as "fountain vomiting" because this symptom is very different from normal vomiting (gastroesophageal reflux) seen at this age. Some babies show poor feeding and weight loss, while others show normal weight gain. Dehydration can also occur, causing babies to cry without tears and not pass urine for hours or days. Another obvious symptom is the hourglass shape of the infant's stomach at the site of peristalsis. In rare cases, pyloric stenosis in infants can occur as an autosomal dominant condition. The pyloric part of the stomach of babies born with such a defect, the sphincter muscles may be congenitally narrowed or functionally hypertrophied. Obstruction of the pyloric part of the stomach is observed due to the hypertrophied pyloric part, and the passage of nutrients from the stomach to the duodenum is disturbed. As a result, all ingested food products and gastric secretions are released into the environment only through vomiting. Vomiting is often "fountain-like". Although the exact cause of hypertrophy remains unknown, several studies have suggested that hyperacidity may be involved in the pathogenesis of neonatal pylorus stenosis in infants. Constant vomiting leads to loss of gastric juice (hydrochloric acid). Vomiting mass does not contain bile

<http://innoconferences.iblogger.org/>

because pyloric obstruction prevents duodenal enzymes (which contain bile) from entering the stomach. The loss of chloride leads to a decrease in the level of chloride in the blood, which impairs the kidney's ability to excrete bicarbonate. As a result, metabolic alkalosis can occur in the baby's body. In addition, secondary hyperaldosteronism develops due to a decrease in blood volume. High concentrations of aldosterone cause the kidneys to retain Na^+ and to excrete large amounts of K^+ in the urine. The body's compensatory response to metabolic alkalosis is hypoventilation, which leads to an increase in the concentration of pCO_2 in arterial blood. The diagnosis is made by taking an anamnesis about the disease, performing physical examinations, and is confirmed by X-ray examinations. Pyloric stenosis should be suspected in any child with severe vomiting. In an objective examination, by palpating the abdomen, an unusual mass can be detected in the epigastric area. This formation, consisting of an enlarged pyloric part, is called an "olivoid formation". Rarely palpable or visible peristaltic waves are also detected as the stomach attempts to move ingested food through the narrowed pyloric portion into the duodenum. Pyloric stenosis is often confirmed by ultrasound. On ultrasound examination, it can be seen that the pyloric part is thickened and the mass in the stomach does not pass into the duodenum. In infants less than 30 days of age, a muscular wall thickness of 3 mm or more and a pyloric duct length of 15 mm or more are considered abnormal. If the mass inside the stomach passes through the pyloric part into the duodenum, in such cases pylorostenosis and pylorospasm are diagnosed by mutual comparison. For the purposes of comparative diagnosis, attention should be paid to the position of the superior mesenteric artery and superior mesenteric vein, since the changes in these two vessels may negate pyloric stenosis and instead indicate intestinal malrotation. Although the baby receives radiation, the upper part of the stomach and intestinal

<http://innocoferences.iblogger.org/>

tract is examined by x-ray using contrast agents. A "string sign" or "railway/double track sign" is seen on a post-contrast X-ray in pylorus stenosis. A simple x-ray of the abdomen shows an enlarged stomach. Although pyloric stenosis can be detected during endoscopic examination of the upper gastrointestinal tract, it is not possible to distinguish whether the cause of this stenosis is muscle hypertrophy or pylorospasm. In blood tests, as a result of constant vomiting, gastric acid (which contains hydrochloric acid) is often released into the environment, resulting in an increase in blood pH and a decrease in potassium and chloride levels. An exchange of extracellular potassium with intracellular hydrogen ions occurs to correct the pH balance. Pyloric stenosis is usually treated with surgery. and in very rare cases, conservative treatment may help. The danger of pylorostenosis is not the closure of the pyloric part, but its complication is dehydration and electrolyte imbalance. Therefore, first of all, it is necessary to provide help aimed at preventing dehydration of the baby and normalizing the pH level in the blood. Usually, such assistance should be carried out in the first 24-48 hours, if not delayed. Intravenous and oral atropine can be used to treat pyloric stenosis. Pyloromyotomy surgery has a success rate of 85-89%. However, for this procedure, patients are required to stay in the hospital for a long time and receive qualified nursing care. This operation is performed through a single incision (usually 3-4 cm long) or laparoscopically (through several small incisions), depending on the experience of the surgeon. Today, the practice of pyloromyotomy through the laparoscopic method (a small circular incision around the navel) has significantly improved and has led to a decrease in the number of open surgical procedures. Because in contrast to open surgical operations performed in the old "Ramstedt" method, the risk of developing wound infections and other complications in laparoscopic operations is low. Although laparoscopic pyloromyotomy is the standard of care for pylorostenosis in

<http://innoconferences.iblogger.org/>

most children's hospitals in the United States, the open Ramstedt method is used by some state surgeons.

References:

1. Pyloric stenosis a 100 years after Ramstedt". Archives of Disease in Childhood 97 (8): 741–5. August 2012. doi:10.1136/archdischild-2011-301526. PMID 22685043.
2. "Infantile hypertrophic pyloric stenosis: epidemiology, genetics, and clinical update". Advances in Pediatrics 58 (1): 195–206. 2011.
3. "Pyloric stenosis in pediatric surgery: an evidence-based review". The Surgical Clinics of North America 92 (3): 527–39, vii-viii. June 2012.